

Swinostics

Swine diseases field diagnostics toolbox

Newsletter N° 5 - October 2021

The project is funded by Horizon 2020, the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation for 2014-2020 under grant agreement No 771649.

SUSTAINABLE FOOD SECURITY – RESILIENT AND RESOURCE-EFFICIENT VALUE CHAINS
Call identifier: H2020-SFS-2016-2017

www.swinostics.eu
 Coordinator: CyRIC
 Dr. Panayiotis Philimis

Swinostics news:

In this period, after laboratory tests and optimization, the SWINOSTICS device was ready to operate in the field. Samples (oral, fecal, and blood) were collected and analyzed directly at the farm by the SWINOSTICS device. The obtained data were sent to a cloud archive for further analysis, sharing and storage (Figures 1-10).

Fig. 1 Oral fluid sample collection.

Fig. 2 Fecal sample collection.

Fig. 3 Blood sample collection.

Fig. 4 Sample filtering pre-treatment.

Fig. 5 SWINOSTICS device.

Fig. 7 Installed PIC.

Fig. 6 SWINOSTICS device front face.

Fig. 8 SWINOSTICS App.

Fig. 9 SWINOSTICS device ready for the analyses.

Fig. 10 Analysis results.

✓ M36 Project meeting

The **SWINOSTICS 36M** meeting organized by CyRIC took place remotely, due to the COVID-19 outbreak restrictions, on the 06th October 2020. All partners attended the event. The focus of the discussions was:

- ✓ PIC mass production
- ✓ Testing of the prototype
- ✓ Prototype validation using real samples (focus on oral fluid samples)
- ✓ Swinostics software for automatic measurements optimization
- ✓ Cloud software optimization
- ✓ Dissemination and communication activities
- ✓ Swinostics workshop organization

36M Meeting SWINOSTICS Project
6th October 2020 – Remote meeting

Main Technical Deliverables M36-M48

- D1.3** Data management plan v2
- D5.4** Field testing prototypes
- D5.5** Report on field samples testing
- D6.2** Field trials assessment report
- D6.3** Device performance assessment report
- D6.4** Trials impact assessment and system usability report
- D7.2** Dissemination and communication activities report and material
- D7.3** (Preliminary version of) Business plan
- D7.4** (Update of) Standardisation requirements, compliance to methodologies and interaction with working groups
- FTR** Final Technical Report

✓ Planned events:

- The final consortium meeting will take place remotely in October 2021.
- The Final Review meeting will take place remotely on the 20th of January 2022.

Swinostics Dissemination activity

✓ Conference and articles

✓The SWINOSTICS project was presented by CyRIC and UVMB in the: Smart Farming Conference! The conference is part of the Photonics Applications Week. Interesting discussions and great audience!

Moderator: Alessandro Giusti, R&D Director, **CyRIC**, [Read more](#)
[Watch presentation](#)

D.O. presentation: Paraskeva Domestidou, Senior Research and Development Engineer, **CyRIC** or "Swine diseases' diagnostic toolbox", [Read more](#)
[Watch presentation](#)

D.O. presentation: Gyuha Eukis, Associate Professor, **University of Veterinary Medicine Budapest** or "Swine diseases' field diagnostic toolbox", [Read more](#)
[Watch presentation](#)

✓An article about SWINOSTICS was published on Open Access Government! Alessandro Giusti from CyRIC presented the project in a interview.

HOME NEWS PUBLICATIONS SPECIAL REPORTS STAKEHOLDERS EBOOKS SUBSCRIBE

Open Access Government

SWINOSTICS: Field-diagnostics in pig farming

14th July 2021

Here, R&D Director Alessandro Giusti details the work of the Horizon 2020 funded **SWINOSTICS** project to tackle

PROFILE

SWINOSTICS: Field-diagnostics in pig farming

Here, R&D Director Alessandro Giusti details the work of the Horizon 2020 funded **SWINOSTICS** project to tackle viruses causing epidemics in pig farming.

The increased population density in modern animal production systems has made them vulnerable to various transboundary zoonotic agents that threaten productivity of the meat industry and even human health. Even though more effective drugs and vaccines have reduced the direct burden of livestock diseases, the total impact of animal health threats now actually is increasing, because in a globalised and highly interconnected world, the effects of diseases extend far beyond animal systems and mortality. As the OIE Director General stated in 2019, "The origins of animal origin are an important and growing global threat to human and animal health, food security, food safety, poverty reduction and biodiversity". The European Commission has also underlined the importance of animal health and the EU added value, through events and presentations of the [EU Joint Action Strategic Science for Health and Consumers](#). A key goal of EU's strategy for animal health is to ensure early diagnosis, to prevent and reduce animal diseases.

Therefore, early diagnosis and establishment of reliable countermeasures to infectious disease outbreaks is essential to limit severe biological and socio-economic consequences.

weeks or months. Thus, the need for the development of mobile diagnostic units has been recently recognised. Reliable and simple diagnostic testing directly on-site would enable rapid, on-the-spot decision making which is crucial to prevent further spreading of the disease.

The SWINOSTICS project
SWINOSTICS is a four-year research project, funded under the EU Horizon 2020 framework programme. The project has a total budget of about 4.5 million Euro, it is being developed by a multi-disciplinary team of ten partners from six EU countries, coordinated by [CyRIC - Cyprus Research and Innovation Center Ltd.](#)

The project addresses the aforementioned need for reliable and fast, on-site diagnostics for pig farms, by developing a novel next-use device, based on advanced, proven, low-cost sensing and photonics technologies. Even though the approach is applicable to a variety of infectious agents, **SWINOSTICS** is focused on emerging and endemic zoonotic African Swine Fever virus, European Borna Disease and Respiratory Syndrome virus, Porcine parvovirus, Porcine circovirus type 2, Classical Swine Fever virus. Swine influenza virus) during epidemics in pig farms in Europe that lead to economic losses.

to that of commercial and institutional laboratories. The device is easily transportable and provides results in less than 45 minutes for four and four for other types of samples simultaneously, in a single highly suitable for use in a field. The modular construction of the core allows future upgrades to increase capacity if so desired.

The SWINOSTICS technology in a nutshell
 The heart of the **SWINOSTICS** system is its photonic integrated circuit (PIC) biosensor. In a nutshell, the way that the sensor works is the following: The surface of the PIC is functionalised with antibodies against the target viruses. This, in turn, allows the antibodies to be bound on the surface of the sensor. Once a sample containing the target virus is detected, the virus binds to the antibodies, and the antibody binding to the virus is detected.

Swinostics Dissemination activity

✓ Conference and articles

A new project leaflet and press release were realized during this period and were disseminated in electronic format through the project website and social-media channels of the project

Figure 11. Last version of leaflet

Figure 12. Last press release of SWINOSTICS project

✓ Swinostics Workshop

The Swinostics workshop took place on Friday 29th October 2021. Multiple stakeholders attended the workshop.

WORKSHOP

SWINOSTICS - Swine diseases field diagnostics toolbox

Coordinator: **CyRIC – Cyprus research and innovation center Ltd**
Friday, 29 October 2021 Start: 09:00 CET

Venue: Online - [Link](#)

Program	
09:00 - 09:15	Connection to the call
09:15 - 09:30	Welcome and project introduction

Figure 13. Workshop Agenda

Swinostics Consortium

